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Federal University of Technology, Akure

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School of Agriculture and
Agricultural Technology

**PERFORMANCE OF GRAVID WEST AFRICAN DWARF
DOES FED MULBERRY LEAVES (MORUS ALBA) AND
GUINEA GRASS (PANICUM MAXIMUM) SUPPLEMENTED
WITH CASSAVA PEEL BASED CONCENTRATE**

BY

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AUGUST, 2021

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SUPPLEMENTED WITH CASSAVA PEEL BASED CONCENTRATE

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CERTIFICATION

BY THE STUDENT

I certify that this work was carried out by ADESINA, OLUWATOBI SAMUEL (APH/15/1419) has not been presented elsewhere for the award of a degree or any other purpose.

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DEDICATION

This report is dedicated to the Glory of God.

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ABSTRACT

The feed intake and growth performance of gravid West African Dwarf does were investigated. Twenty-five does weighing 11.00-16.00kg were used for the study. The does were fed on diets formulated such that diet A contained 100% Panicum maximum (P100MO), diet B contained 75% Panicum maximum + 25% Morus alba (P75M25), diet C contained 50% Panicum maximum + 50% Morus alba (PSOMSO), diet D contained 25% Panicum maximum + 75% Morus alba (P25M75) and diet E contained 100% Morus alba (POM100) respectively. The does were randomly allocated to the five diets with five animals per diet each serving as a replicate. The WAD does were weighed and brought to heat (oestrus) through synchronization using Prostaglandin 2F alpha administered intramuscularly. Bucks of proven stock were allowed to serve the does. Does were evaluated in a pregnancy trial and were weighed at mating and fortnightly until kidding. Parameters investigated were feed intake, nutrient intake and weight gained during pregnancy.

Feed intake reveals that does fed diet C recorded the highest total dry matter intake (TDMI) throughout the three trimesters (356.63, 488.69 and 539.63g/day) respectively when compared to does fed with the other diets. The nutrient intake also show that animals fed diet E had the highest crude protein intake value (180.14g/day) with the lowest acid detergent fibre intake value (235.47g/day). Animals fed diet C recorded the highest daily weight gain (60.19g/day) while the least daily weight gain (37.27g/day) was recorded for animals on diet A. The best feed conversion ratio (14.38) was recorded in animal fed diet C. It can therefore be concluded that the substitution of panicum maximum with /morus alba with inclusion level of up to 50% could

serve as good source of energy and protein in ruminant diets and can also improve growth without any deleterious effects on the animals during gestation.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Livestock are domesticated animals raised in an agricultural setting to obtain products such as food, fleece, and for work (Swanepoel *et al.*, 2010). The increase in world population particularly in developing countries like Nigeria results in the pressing need to improve animal production to meet animal protein needs. Animal protein contents in diets of many Nigerians are very low and have reached a crisis level. Average consumption of animal protein in Nigeria is estimated at 4.5g/head/day as against the prerequisite of 35g/head/day recommended by the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (Rossi *et al.*, 2017).

Nutrition in livestock plays a major role in the overall productivity and the wellbeing of the animals as feed records the largest proportion (60-70%) of the total cost of intensive animal production (Abiola *et al.*, 2016). Its insufficiency in supply in terms of the quality and quantity may bring about a condition referred to as low nutritional status in farm animals which will consequently result to low productivity in such deprived animals. It is therefore vital for animal producer to give more attention to animal nutrition if their aim is to yield maximum productivity.

Hence, to meet the nutritional requirement of these animals, this calls for looking for alternative feed resources such as agro-industrial waste and crop residue which could be used as supplement to improve and support animal performance and productivity to ensure meeting up with the animal protein (especially from goats) demand by human being (Makkar, 2016).

Goats were the first wild herbivores to be domesticated in the Near East around eleven thousand years ago towards the start of the revolutionary change from hunter-gatherer to agriculture-based societies (Kelly *et al.*, 2016).

Mulberry (*Morus spp.*) is widely cultivated in Nigeria and different nations. Mulberry (*Morus alba L.*) leaves, are generally utilized as feed of silk worm (Butt *et al.*, 2008). Mulberry leaves have been recognized as an phenomenal food resource with high content of protein, carbohydrate, vitamins, micro-elements and dietary fiber (Srivastava *et al.*, 2006). Some reports demonstrated that mulberry leaves had high content of bioactive compounds including phenolic acids, flavonoids, alkaloids and γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA) (Chan *et al.*, 2016; Milera *et al.*, 2011). The Mulberry (*Morus alba*) tree is a perennial woody plant which belongs to the family *Moraceae*. The tree is recognized as food plant for silkworm as well as an economic tree (Jaiyeola and Adeduntan, 2002).

Panicum maximum is one of the most productive native pastures in tropical areas and produces high yields of palatable fodder. *Panicum maximum* is found in abundance in the savanna region of Nigeria (Idowu *et al.*, 2020). Cassava peel is a source of energy in polygastric feeding and it is highly digestible due to its high soluble carbohydrate content (Ajayi and Omotoso, 2018). It is affordable and accessible all through the year due to the large quantity of cassava tuber produced for diverse uses (Ibhaze, 2015).

This study was therefore designed to evaluate the performance of gravid West African dwarf doe fed Mulberry leaves (*Morus alba*) and Guinea grass (*Panicum maximum*) supplemented with cassava peel based concentrate.

1.1 Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of this research are to:

- i. determine the chemical composition (proximate, phytochemical and mineral) of *Panicum maximum*, *Morus alba* leaves and cassava peel-based concentrate;
- ii. assess the feed intake, growth rate, feed conversion ratio of WAD does fed the experimental diets during pregnancy.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Goats

Goats are one of man's principal sources of meat and milk. Most goats are found in the drier areas of the developing world. The total world population in 2007 was estimated at about 850 million goats of which 728 million were in low income food deficit countries (FAO STAT, 2008). Asia is home to about 545 million goats and Africa to about 245 million: these two areas, therefore, are the major repositories of the goat. The 14 countries of West Africa contain about 81 million goats (Daramola and Adeloje, 2009). Many of this number south of latitude 14°N which is humid and provides an environment favourable to high disease challenge are of the West African Dwarf (WAD) type. The WAD has many recognized subtypes (Daramola and Adeloje, 2009). Under this humid tropical climate heat stress and disease challenge are compounded by inadequate nutrition, poor housing and rudimentary management. Under these conditions it is to be expected that animals are often in poor condition and often fail to perform to their potential. Physiological changes occur when animals are stressed but paramount and fundamental are loss of form (weight), loss of performance (production) and loss of life (death). This notwithstanding the WAD is hardy and thrives in harsh conditions of management which is largely possible because of the innate adaptogenic power of the animal to react to a particular quantum stressor (Daramola *et al.*, 2015).

The abundance of WAD goats in the tropical humid areas of the West African coastal and hinterland areas reflects a better adaptation of this species to these environments when compared to sheep (which in Nigeria and elsewhere) are usually confined to the drier areas (Chiejina and Behnke, 2011). The tropical humid agro-climatic zone is infested with tsetse fly and the dwarf goat thrives well and reproduces with twin and triplet births in this ecological niche. The breed is often

referred to as achondro-plastic as it has disproportionately short legs which are often bent and the body length appears long for the size (Pagabeleguem *et al.*, 2016). The coat is short and shows a range of colours from black to brown and white and there are many mixtures of these colours. It is believed that coat colour and certain breed characteristics provide this breed with unique abilities (Daramola and Adeloje, 2009). The ears are short and erect and point forwards. In its home area the WAD is a preferred meat animal but milk production is poor. The male stands 22 cm at the withers and weighs 18kg at maturity whereas the female stands 18cm and weighs 15kg at maturity (Daramola *et al.*, 2015).

The West African Dwarf goat is acceptable to all religions. It features prominently as a slaughter animal at ceremonial occasions and festivals. It serves as source of income and investment against failure of cash crops. Ecological conditions, feed resources and interactions with the cropping subsystem determine the goat management system. With few exceptions goats are allowed to range free during the drier parts of the year but are tethered or stall fed in the cropping season: at night goats are kept in open camps or confined in pens or houses (Aziiba, 2015). Much of the feed of these goats is scavenged from the local environment but most are also given some kitchen waste (Adeloje and Daramola, 2004). There appears to be a general consensus that goats indigenous to harsh environment perform better than other domestic ruminants' indifferent environmental conditions (Kim *et al.*, 2016).

Goats are multipurpose animal providing milk, meat, fertilizer, clothing, offering loyalty and companionship; they are alert, intelligent and socially inclined. This animal forms an important economic and ecological niche in agricultural systems throughout developing countries. Goats are one of the first animals to be domesticated by man, and they are among the cleanest of all farm animals (NRC, 2007). The does and kids are odourless, but the mature bucks do have a musk-like

odour, especially during the breeding season; but with proper management the scent is not overly offensive. They can be raised easily in all climates and do not need elaborate housing. The Nigerian Dwarf goat has been internationally recognized as dairy and companion animal since 1854.

2.1.1 Scientific Classification and Description of Goat (*Capra hircus*)

It was reported by Animal Bytes, (2010) that goats originated from the mountainous areas of West Asia and Eastern Europe, grazing on hillsides and plains. Modern day, common goats are known as domesticated goats.

Kingdom: *Animalia*

Phylum: *Chordata*

Class: *Mammalia*

Order: *Artiodactyla*

Family: *Bovidae*

Genus: *Capra*

2.1.2 Description of Goat

The domestic goat (*Capra hircus*) comes from the wild goat. Their products like meat, milk, fur and skin are eaten and used by people. With goat milk, cheese can be made, along with other dairy products. Goats are used to keep grasses and other plants from getting too tall (Mutua, 2019). Some farmers use goats to remove unwanted plants like weeds.

The domestic goat has clove hooves, a long beard on its chin, a short tail that turns up, and horns that grow up from the head in an arc. The hair is straight with a woolly coat under it during winter. The domestic goat is about 70 – 120cm (24 – 48inches) tall. They weigh from 45 – 54kg (100 – 120lb). The diet of the domestic goats includes eating grass, leaves shrubs and unwanted plants

from their pastures. Goats living in the desert, where plants are quite hard to find, have been seen climbing trees to get food (Coffey *et al.*, 2008).

2.1.3 The West African Dwarf (WAD) Goat

West African Dwarf goats breed are believed to be brought from East and North Africa, particular Somalia where dwarf goats are also found, the West African Dwarf is the progenitor of the African pygmy and Nigerian Dwarf breed in the United States (Adewale, 2012).

The West African Dwarf goat breed probably evolved in response to the conditions in the humid forests of West and Central Africa. The breed is known by some other names in different parts of the world such as *African Dwarf*, *Chevre naine de Savanes*, *Cameroon Dwarf*, *Chevre de Casamance*, *Chevre naine de l'est*, *Djallonke*, *Dwarf West African*, *Diougry*, *Forest goat*, *Fouta Djallon*, *Grassland Dwarf*, *Guinean*, *Guinean Dwarf*, *Kosi*, *Pygmy*, *Tibetana* etc (Rotimi *et al.*, 2017).

West African Dwarf goat is usually smaller in size. Both bucks and does have horns. Their horns are curve outwards in does and backwards in bucks. The bucks also have beards, and sometimes manes. Their chest is broad and the back straight and their neck is relatively long. The legs of the West African Dwarf goat are short. Udder of the does is small but usually well-shaped. Most of the goats have short stiff hair. And the color varies; dark brown with black points is probably the most common, but black, red, white, pied and multi-colored goats also occur. The common colors are; black, brown and sometimes white with color markings (Alokan, 2008). They have a typical height of 12 to 20 inches (30 to 50 cm). And the adult bucks on average weight about 20 to 25 kg, and the does about 18 to 22 kg.

In most cases, the West African Dwarf goats are capable of breeding at 12 to 18 months of age. Multiple births are very common with twins being normal and triplets frequent.

The kidding interval averages about 220 days. They are very important in the rural economy of West Africa. Most of the rural families of West Africa used to keep these goats for meat production. The West African dwarf (WAD) goats are predominantly found in the southern part of Nigeria, which is humid and favours high prevalence of diseases (Khandoker *et al.*, 2018). The goats are hardy, with the ability to thrive and survive under harsh environmental conditions of heat and humidity and the ability to thrive in tse-tse fly infested humid forests and guinea savannah zones (Oseni and Ajayi, 2014). West African Dwarf goats are not seasonal breeders, they are prolific breed and selection could help meet the need for the animal protein (Fidelis and Kahan, 2007).

2.1.4 Prolific Nature of Goats

The indigenous goats breed throughout the year with the highest kidding in raining season which coincides with optimum feed availability. Goats are early breeders, reaching puberty at 6 to 7 months of age. The age at which they first kid is between 16 and 18 months. The gestation length for WAD sheep and goats is found to be 145 to 148 days (Kubkomawa *et al.*, 2017). The kidding interval of 220 days. The shortest interval generally occurs in traditional systems where uncontrolled breeding is the norm. Thus in effect the WAD goats, under rural conditions kid three times in two years. In the period of two years, it is possible for a doe to give birth to six kids because of its high twinning rate. This quick turn over rate is an advantage to producer in terms of cash flow and the building up of his or her herd size (Coffey, 2006).

2.1.5 Goat as food product

In sub-Saharan Africa, goats account for about 11% of the total meat output (Rege and Lebbies, 2000). Goat meat is the meat of the domestic goat (*Capra aegagrus hircus*).

Goat meat from adults is often called chevon and *cabrito*, *capretto* or *kid* when it is from young animals. Goat is both a staple and a delicacy in world's cuisines. Goat meat is savory and less sweet than beef but slightly sweeter than lamb (Li *et al.*, 2020). It can be prepared in a variety of ways, such as being stewed, curried, baked, grilled, barbecued, minced, canned, fried or made into sausage. Goat jerky is also another popular variety. Despite being classified as red meat, goat is leaner and contains less cholesterol, fat, and protein than both lamb and beef (Webb, 2014) and less energy than beef or chicken (Scarborough *et al.*, 2011) therefore, it requires low-heat, slow cooking to preserve tenderness and moisture. One reason for the leanness is that goats do not accumulate fat deposits or marbling in their muscles (Coffey *et al.*, 2008).

2.1.6 Opportunity and Challenges facing goat production

There are several opportunities for small-scale farmers to supplement their incomes by integrating small ruminants into their farm enterprises. Such opportunities are created by several factors such as the rising demand for goat meat, the low start-up cost, the minimal labor requirements, the ability to use the animals for brush control and multi-species grazing, in addition to the prolific nature of goats (Okpebholo and Kahan, 2007).

Although there are many opportunities for limited-resource farmers who decide to enter into the small ruminant industry, the challenges that influence their success are real and must be addressed.

The main challenges that have created the largest obstacles to the development of a viable small ruminant industry in the country are lack of an effective means to control internal parasites, lack of effective marketing strategies for products derived from goat meat, inadequate expertise

information, and limited access for limited-resource farmers to financial support (Aina and Oppong, 2011).

2.1.7 Digestion in WAD

Like other vertebrates, WADs are unable to digest plant material directly, because they lack enzymes to break down cellulose in the cell walls. Digestion in ruminants occurs sequentially in a four-chambered stomach. Plant material is initially taken into the rumen, where it is processed mechanically and exposed to bacteria that can break down cellulose (foregut fermentation) (Parish *et al.*, 2017). The reticulum allows the animal to regurgitate and reprocess particulate matter ("*chew its cud*"). More finely-divided food is then passed to the omasum, for further mechanical processing. The mass is finally passed to the true stomach, the abomasum, where the digestive enzyme lysozyme breaks down the bacteria so as to release nutrients. Use of plant material is thus indirect, with primary processing by the bacterial flora maintained in the stomach. In kids of up to 6 weeks of age, the rumen is relatively under-developed and as the animal begins to eat solid food, the reticular-rumen enlarges greatly until in adulthood, then it consists of 85% of the total capacity of the stomach (Wu *et al.*, 2014).

2.2 Management System of Goats

2.2.1 Extensive management system

Under this type of system, goats are on free range, they are allowed to browse freely. Feed resources under this management system are those obtained by scavenging around households through grazing and browsing on natural vegetable in natural pasture, fallow lands or along roadsides and sometime household waste. No special provision of forage or good housing with proper management for them, little attention is paid to adequate feeding and health of animals. Goats are sometimes provided with household and kitchen wastes which could include yam

cassava, and plantain peel, the bran of rice and other grains and pods of beans. The animals supplement this with bush grazing (Amole *et al.*, 2014). The system of management is cheap and less labour intensive. It is characterized by low productivity and high losses due to accidents, diseases and theft (Ajala *et al.*, 2008).

2.2.2 Semi-intensive management system

Semi-intensive system of goat production is an intermediate compromise between extensive and intensive system followed in some flocks having limited grazing. It involves extensive management but usually with controlled grazing of fenced pasture. It consists of provision of stall feeding, shelter at night under shed and 3 to 5 hour daily grazing and browsing on pasture and range. In this method the feed cost somewhat increased. It is a system that typically combines grazing and the utilization of crop residues and by-products with some form of arable cropping (Caballero *et al.*, 2011). In addition, the goats are supplemented with concentrates and mineral salt. Water is made available all the time. Mating is controlled by separating the buck and does. In most cases, the bucks are completely stall-fed and females on heat are brought to the buck for mating. This is important as it helps to control the off-flavour in milk and inbreeding. This type of management is found on government farms. It also helps in making a profitable gain due to less labour input (Khan *et al.*, 2018).

2.2.3 Intensive management system

It is a system in which goats are continuously kept under housing in confinement with limited access to land or otherwise so called zero grazing system of goat production in which they are stall fed. It is a goat production system where good housing and hand-feeding is proved for the animals. It implies a system where goats are not left to fend for themselves with only minimum care, this has the advantage of close supervision and control over the animals in feeding, diseases and

breeding (Singh and Chauhan, 2017). It prevents crop damage by the animals and reduces risks of accidents. It provides the opportunity for better management, but several additional costs are involved apart from the costs of the shed itself. Feed resources under confinement systems also include feedstuffs collected from range by the farmer and fed to the animals. Farmers also provide feed concentrates or agro-industrial by-products. This system of management requires more labour and high cash input (Prüss-Üstün *et al.*, 2016).

2.3 Nutrition in Goat

Big efforts have been developed to understand the rumen physiology and environment. Thus, Wang *et al.* (2009) investigated the crude protein and starch degradation in goat rumen in different feedstuffs. Modern nutrition is the basis for improving goat production in developing countries using their own feedstuff or feed resources and is usually poorly studied by developing countries. López-Aliaga *et al.* (2010) study the relationship between the physical forms of alfalfa on methane production in Murciano-Granadina goats, observing differences between long or chopped alfalfa and differences in the combination with corn or barley. This is one of the major nutrition research topics for the future.

Energy expenditure has been an important topic for the last few years. Beker *et al.* (2009) have greatly improved the study of the energy expenditure of goats in pasture by studying how it is influenced by stocking rate (SR), breed and stage of production. The same research group (Beker *et al.* 2010) completed the energy studies by observing the activity energy cost for different types of goats as well as a breed of sheep. More research is necessary to understand how goats in different environments and production systems use the energy. Tovar-Luna *et al.* (2010a) study the effects of stage of lactation and dietary concentrate level on energy utilization by Alpine dairy goats,

concluding that despite differences in nutrient requirement expressions, observations of this study supported National Research Council recommendations of the energy requirements of lactating dairy goats. Tovar-Luna *et al.* (2010b) studied the combined effects of stage of lactation and level of feed intake on energy utilization by Alpine dairy goats, concluding that the level of feed intake can have substantial effect on estimates of energy utilization by lactating dairy goats.

Nutrition in the last few years has been focused on the search for new vegetal species to feed goats. Alamer (2009) reports the use of *Foeniculum vulgare* Millin dairy goats, using Rhodes grass diets as a control, with no differences between diets for milk yield, milk production efficiency, milk composition and feed intake. Other authors (Kamalak *et al.* 2010) investigated the use of young, old and senescent leaves of *Arbutus* and *rachne*, concluding that the *A. andrachnetree* could be considered moderate quality forage for sheep and goats. However, senescent leaves are only low-quality forage. In the same way, Salem (2010) discussed the use of *Atriplex nummulariata* feed goat and sheep.

New strategies of goat nutrition have been implemented. Molina-Alcaide *et al.* (2010) studied the effects of partial replacement of concentrate with feed blocks on nutrient utilization, microbial N flow, and milk yield and composition in goats, observing good results when feed blocks were used but reduced milk yield. The philosophy ‘from farm to fork’ can be applied to the goat sector nowadays. Pereira *et al.* (2010) tried to modify milk quality by adding castor or licuri oil to the goats’ diet. Observing the sensory analysis results, a low acceptability was observed for milk from goats supplemented with castor oil, but licuri oil supplementation led to higher acceptability scores for flavor and odor of goat milk.

Betaine has played an important role in goat milk production in the last few years. Trying to understand the role of oral betaine in goat milk production, Fernandez *et al.* (2009) used two groups

of 30 goats to determine the effects of added betaine, but no significant differences between groups were observed for milk yield, chemical composition and somatic cells count in milk. Betaine-supplemented diets increased relatively the proportions of short chain fatty acids.

The relationship between nutrition and physiology has also played an important role in the last few years. Thus, Schonhusein *et al.* (2010) studied the morphology, the proliferation and ribonucleic acid and fractional protein syntheses in the small intestinal mucosa of young goats fed on soy protein-based diets with or without amino acid supplementation, concluding that soy protein feeding resulted in changes in intestinal growth associated with effects on intestinal RNA and protein synthesis, but that were not ameliorated by amino acid supplementation.

2.4 Reproduction in Goat

Reproductive fitness may be regarded as the most important criterion relating to adaptation. From the onset of its reproductive life the WAD goat has established itself as a most productive and prolific breeder. The WAD goat attains puberty at the relatively early age. Although age at puberty is highly variable and is dependent on the genetic type of the animals and the management system in the tropical environment puberty in indigenous goats occurs at 8 to 14 months of age (Daramola and Adeloje, 2009). An older age at puberty has been given for WAD goats but this appears to result from poor management conditions. Puberty begins when at least some of the morphological traits (testes size over 6g, appearance of seminiferous tubules and commencement of spermatogenesis) are present (Daramola and Adeloje, 2009).

The economic viability of livestock exploitation is closely related to animals attaining sexual maturity at a precocious age which means more offspring could be produced during an animal's life. Attempts have been made to induce puberty in WAD bucks. Melatonin, a hormone produced by the pineal gland has been reported to have an effect on the activity of the testes, semen

production and puberty (Celi *et al.*, 2017). WAD buck-kids display onset of spermatozoa release in the ejaculate at 5 months old when administered with exogenous melatonin. Although WAD goats display interesting reproductive characteristics and could attain puberty at an early age there exists a strong influence of the environment which does not allow these potentials to be fully expressed (Daramola *et al.*, 2007).

Notwithstanding the fact that the WAD goat is generally left to scavenge and cater for its own nourishment this breed is prolific with a litter size of as much as 1.85. Improvement beyond this to higher litter sizes maybe counterproductive as mortality rates of kids can be high with prolificacy values exceeding 2.00 especially when kids which have no access to teats are not artificially fed. High mortality rates of kids (36.34%) are a source of wastage but this can be reduced with proper management practices. There can be a substantial increase in reproductive performance of WAD goats kept under a highly intensive model. Productivity (live weight production per goat) more than doubles from 10.9 kg live weight per goat year in the extensive model to 24.2 kg in the high intensive model. The difference has been linked to higher average litter size at birth and higher survival rate of weaners and growers (Daramola and Adeloye, 2009). Daily sperm production (DSP) values obtained by both quantitative histology and from testicular homogenates was higher in WAD bucks than values reported for Red Sokoto Maradi bucks. Breed differences could be attributed to the variations observed in the sperm production rates and suggest a higher sperm production potential in the WAD buck. In the humid tropics most research workers have observed dwarf goat breeding throughout the year. The seasonal peaks that do occur are more likely the result from fluctuations in feed availability rather than changes in photo-intensity. Gonadal sperm reserves in all seasons have been reported to be higher in WAD bucks than values observed for Red Sokoto Maradi bucks. The same trend has been observed in extra gonadal sperm

reserves thus confirming earlier observations that the WAD bucks might have a higher reproductive capacity in the humid tropical zone than other ruminant species and could be used for breeding purposes all year round (Akpa *et al.*, 2013).

2.5 Mulberry Leaves (*Morus alba*)

Mulberry (*Morus spp.*, *Moraceae*) is a well-known medicinal plant. White mulberry (*Morus alba*), black mulberry (*M. nigra*) and red mulberry (*M. rubra*) are the most notable species of the genus *Morus* (Yigit *et al.*, 2010). Different species of mulberry are distributed in tropical, subtropical and temperate areas throughout the world. However, the majority of the plant is widespread in Asian countries, such as China, Japan, Korea and India (Sarkar *et al.*, 2018).

Mulberry is a multi-functional plant. Being an excellent source of nutrients and phyto-chemicals, mulberry has been established as functional food (Srivastava *et al.*, 2006). The fresh fruits are edible and harvested for food production, such as juice, jam and jelly (Yigit *et al.*, 2010). Meanwhile, the leaves are highly palatable (Srivastava *et al.*, 2006). Mulberry leaves play a pivotal role in the sericulture industry because they serve as the sole food of silkworm (*Bombyx mori*). The leaves are also cultivated for dairy animal feed due to the positive effect on milk production. Herbal tea made from mulberry leaves are consumed as a healthy beverage among Asian countries (Chan *et al.*, 2016). In the folk remedies, various parts of mulberry tree, including root bark, leaves and fruits, have been traditionally used for the treatment of fever, cough, hyperlipidaemia, hypertension and hyperglycaemia (Chan *et al.*, 2016). Mulberry leaves-derived products in the form of powders, extracts and capsules are now commercially available as functional foods and dietary supplements for controlling body weight and blood glucose.

Scientific studies suggest that mulberry leaves contain a cluster of bioactive compounds and possess several pharmacological effects. Nonetheless, evidence demonstrating beneficial effects

of mulberry leaves against cardio metabolic risks remains scarce at present. It is known that the protein, carbohydrate, vitamins, microelements, and dietary fiber are the main factors influencing nutritional quality of vegetables. However, bioactive compounds and their bioactivity were considered high concerned factors when they were used as special tea or materials of functional foods. Both the nutrients and bioactive compounds could have synergistically beneficial effects on human health. Mulberry leaves have been identified as an excellent food resource with high content of protein, carbohydrate, vitamins, microelements, and dietary fiber (Butt *et al.*, 2008 and Srivastava *et al.*, 2006).

Some reports indicated that mulberry leaves had high content of bioactive compounds, including phenolic acids, flavonoids, alkaloids, and γ -aminobutyric acid (GABA). These compounds had been confirmed to involve in anti-oxidation, decreasing glycemia, antihypertensive, preventing atherosclerosis, and anti-inflammation. 1-deoxynojirimycin (DNJ), as one of the main bioactive compounds in mulberry, is a potent inhibitor of α -glycosidases and has shown potential therapeutic effects on many diseases, particularly type II diabetes (Yu *et al.*, 2018).

2.5.1 Medicinal Properties of Mulberry

Mulberry leaves containing sugars, rutin, quercetin, volatile oil, amino acid, vitamins and microelements that have so many pharmacological activities such as reducing blood glucose, anti-hyperlipidemia, hypertensive, bacteriostatic and antiviral (Ramesh, *et al.*, 2014). Bio active compounds in different species of mulberry can enhance lifespan (Sigdel *et al.*, 2018). Different pharmaceutical properties of mulberry plants are reviewed by many scientists and they have reported that, many biochemical compounds such as Moranoline, Albufuran, Albanol, Morusin, Kuwanol, Calystegine and Hydroxymorcin are isolated from mulberry plants play an important role in pharmaceutical industry (Ramesh *et al.*, 2014). Medicinal properties of mulberry plants are

identified for their profitable medicinal value and therefore attracted the attention of pharmaceutical research and industry.

Mulberry contains plentiful nutritious elements such as minerals and vitamins; it can cure chronic diseases of the digestive tract, promote gastric juice secretion, strengthen the ability for digesting and assimilating, improve the appetite and eliminate abdominal distention and constipation.

Mulberry is very well suitable for chronic gastritis, hepatitis and Alzheimer diseases (Shih *et al.*, 2010 and Ha *et al.*, 2012).

2.6 *Panicum maximum*

Panicum maximum is one of the most productive native pastures in tropical areas and produces high yields of palatable fodder. It is one of the most common grasses in the derived savanna region of Nigeria (Ajayi and Babayemi, 2008).

Panicum maximum is a perennial, tufted grass with a short, creeping rhizome. The stems of this robust grass can reach a height of up to 2m. As the stems bend and nodes touch the ground, roots and new plants are formed. The leaf sheaths are found at the bases of the stems and are covered in fine hairs. It remains green until late into winter. The leaf blades are up to 35 mm wide and taper to a long fine point. The inflorescence is a large multi-branched, open panicle with loose, flexuous branches. *Panicum maximum* is highly palatable to ruminant animals and has 23.5-29.9 % DM at harvest (Lawal–Adebowale, 2012). Nitrogen content in *Panicum maximum* ranges from 0.8% to 2.0% dry matter and crude fibre from 29.5 to 42.2% DM, while total digestible nutrients (TDN) can be as high as 10.2% (Zaeem *et al.*, 2021). The native pastures are however known to deteriorate rapidly, especially in the dry season. They decline rapidly in acceptability and digestibility, particularly with crude protein (CP) as low as 2.0 to 3.0 % in some periods of the year and this is

far below the minimum CP requirement of 7.0 to 8.0 % for ruminant livestock maintenance (Devendra and Leng, 2011).

2.7 Cassava peels

Cassava peels can be used as a roughage and as an energy feed in ruminant diets. However, sun drying, ensiling and fermentation should be used to prevent HCN poisoning when feeding bitter cassava varieties (Lukuyu *et al.*, 2014). Cassava peels should not be fed alone, as their protein and mineral content cannot support optimum rumen function and productivity. Their optimal utilization requires supplementation with readily fermentable protein and by-pass protein, as well as micronutrients including sulphur, phosphorus, and vitamin B. If fed in a balanced diet, cassava peels are a valuable feed for ruminants (Yeboah, 2015). Cassava peels are highly digestible products, with reported values of 78% and 81% for DM and OM total tract digestibility respectively (Ojukamaiye *et al.*, 2013). Dry matter degradability is also high, with reported values more than 70%. Cassava peels have a low protein content (<6% DM) and a high and variable fibre content (crude fibre in the 10-30% DM range) (Yitbarek and Tamir, 2014).

Cassava peels can represent 5 to 15% of the root (Aro *et al.*, 2010). They are obtained after the tubers have been water-cleansed and peeled mechanically (Aro *et al.*, 2010). They may contain high amounts of cyanogenic glycosides and have higher protein content than other tuber parts (Nur *et al.*, 2013).

2.8 Feeding in WAD

2.8.1 Roles and Implications of Concentrate Feeding

The primary role of concentrate feeds is to provide concentrated sources of necessary nutrients for livestock production. These nutrients include not only macro-nutrients of energy and protein but also important specific nutrients such as amino acids, fatty acids, enzymes, vitamins, minerals and others. Both monogastric and ruminant livestock are fed concentrates. Monogastric livestock have a limited capacity to digest fibre and thus require diets of higher nutrient density with a higher proportion of concentrate feeds and less roughage, particularly for intensive poultry and pig production systems. Less intensive monogastric production systems may utilize smaller amounts of conventional concentrates to supplement available feeds in the form of wastes or by-products of human food preparation, together with some forage feeds (Niyas *et al.*, 2015).

Many ruminant production systems also use concentrate feeds. In intensive systems, especially for milk production and in fattening periods for meat production, concentrates may form a high proportion of diets (over 30% and 70% respectively) (Okunlola *et al.*, 2015). Ruminant production systems of lower intensity sometimes utilize concentrate feeds to supplement roughage based diets, either to mitigate the seasonality of forage supplies, or to meet the higher nutrient requirements for particular classes of stock or animals in critical physiological states, such as lactating cows, weaner calves or draught animals. Two specific additional consequences of concentrate feeding are important to note in the context of environmental impacts of feed utilization. The first is that improvements in livestock productivity are generally associated with improved biological efficiency of feed use; the second is the role of concentrate feeds in promoting better utilization of roughage feeds for ruminant livestock (Poli *et al.*, 2020).

2.8.2 Utilization of Roughage Feeds

The feeding of small amounts of concentrate feeds can increase the utilization of roughage feeds by ruminant livestock in some feeding systems. Improvements in the digestibility of roughages are due to the provision of necessary nutrients (especially degradable protein) to promote rumen fermentation, resulting in increased fibre digestion and intakes of roughages, reduced wastes from unconsumed and undigested feeds, and increased animal productivity and efficiency (Salami *et al.*, 2010). These effects can be particularly important in feeding systems based on relatively poor quality roughages, such as in many small-holder and semi-intensive ruminant systems. It may be noted, however, that at higher levels of feeding with better quality roughages, and with cereals and/or high-sugar concentrates, substitution effects occur so that fibre digestion and roughage intakes may be reduced by increased concentrate feeding. This occurs particularly in intensive dairy production systems, with the consequences that increases in productivity in these systems may result in an increased demand for concentrate feeds (Orodho, 2019).

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Experimental site

The experiment was conducted at the Small Ruminant Unit of the Teaching and Research Farm, FUTA, Ondo State, Nigeria (Latitude 7° 18" and Longitude 5° 10" E) (Aro *et al.*, 2008). Laboratory analysis was carried out at the Nutrition Laboratories of Animal Production and Health.

3.2 Sourcing and Processing of Feed Materials

Fresh mulberry (*Morus alba*) leaves were collected from Ondo State Ministry of Agriculture Sericulture Project Site, Km 4 Ondo road, Akure while fresh *Panicum maximum* will be sourced from the pasture within FUTA campus. Cassava peel were collected fresh from a commercial 'Garri' processing industry in Igbatoro Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria while other feed ingredients that were used in formulating the experimental concentrate will be sourced from a reputable feed mill in Akure.

The fresh cassava peels were subsequently sun-dried for 4 days on a tarpaulin depending on the intensity of the sun to reduce the moisture and cyanide contents. Thereafter, the cassava peel were crushed, bagged and stored on raised platform.

The experimental concentrate was formulated from the crushed cassava-peel, wheat offal, brewers dried grains, palm kernel cake (PKC), bone meal, premix and salt using the proportions indicated in Table 3.1 and mixed manually. These were bagged and kept in the store on raised wooden platform.

3.3 Experimental Diets

There were five (5) experimental diets that comprised *Morus alba* and *Panicum maximum* fodders, along with a formulated feed concentrate (Table 3.1). A = 100% *Panicum maximum* (P100M0), B = 75% *Panicum maximum* + 25% *Morus alba* (P75M25), C = 50% *Panicum maximum* + 50% *Morus alba* (P50M50), D = 25% *Panicum maximum* + 75% *Morus alba* (P25M75), E = 100% *Morus alba* (P0M100).

Table 3.1: Composition of the formulated cassava-peel based concentrate for experimental WAD goats

INGREDIENTS	DIETS (%)
Cassava peel	52.50
Wheat offal	17.00
Brewers dry grain	17.50
Palm kernel cake	10.00
Bone meal	1.00
Premix	1.00
Salt	1.00
Total	100
Calculated composition	1660.00
Metabolizable Energy (Kcal/kg)	10.00
Crude Protein (%)	13.51
Crude Fibre (%)	0.41
Calcium (%)	0.24
Av. Phosphorus (%)	

3.4 Experimental Animals and their Management

Twenty-five WAD does were used for this trial and the management practices was carried out. The WAD does were weighed and brought to heat (oestrus) through synchronization using Prostaglandin 2F alpha administered intramuscularly. Bucks of proven stock were allowed to serve the does. Pregnancy was affirmed after 30 days non-return to heat. The date of service was also recorded. The animals were fed concentrates at a constant rate by 8.00am while forage were fed ad-libitum by 2.00pm and fresh water was offered daily.

3.5 Laboratory Procedures

3.5.1 Proximate Analysis of Feed

The air-dried sample of folliages were analyzed for dry matter, crude protein, crude fibre, ash and ether extract according to AOAC (2002) procedures. The fibre fractions were determined using the method of (Van Soest 1991).

3.5.1.1 Determination of energy

The gross energy was determined against thermo-chemical –grade benzoic acid using combustion calorimeter (model 2k combustion calorimeter, www.cal2k.com). Each sample was analysed thrice. Metabolizable energy was calculated according to Van Soest and Robertson (1985). The gross energy of the diets was determined by the methods of Ekanayake *et al.*, (1999) as follows.

$$\text{G.E. (KJ/100g DM)} = \% \text{ CP} \times 16.7 + \% \text{ lipids} \times 37.7 + \% \text{ CHO} \times 16.7$$

CHO = Carbohydrate; G.E. = Gross Energy

3.5.1.2 Moisture content determination

This was done using the oven-drying method. Cleaned, dry and well-labeled petri dishes were weighed (W_1). The sample of experimental diets and faeces of 5g each were weighed into the dishes (W_2) and oven-dried at 105⁰C for 3 hours and they were transferred into the desiccators to

cool and weighed (W_3). The process was continued until a constant weight was obtained. The analysis was carried out in duplicate.

3.5.1.3 Determination of crude protein

This involved three stages namely; digestion, distillation and titration.

a. Digestion

This was determination using the kjeldahl method, 0.5kg of each sample of feed, faeces and urine were measure into 500ml kjeldahl flask. Concentrated H_2SO_4 (25ml) and selenium catalyst were added and boiled until the sample change to light blue. It was cooled and made up 50ml with distilled water. The sample was stored in a bottle.

b. Distillation

This was determined by putting 5ml of 2% H_2BO_3 (Boric acid) into conical flask and 2 drops of mixed indicator (0.19g bromocresol green plus 0.132g methyl red into 200ml alcohol) were added. The receiving flask was placed so that the tip of the condenser tube was below the surface of the boric acid. The 5ml of digested sample was pipette into the condensers cup and 10ml of 40% NaOH added, this was washed down with distilled water. The joints were tightened and a volume of 50ml distillate was received in the receiving flask.

c. Titration

The distillate was titrated against 0.1ml HCl. The colour change was from green to stint blue until the end point (light pink colour) was reached.

$$\% \text{ Nitrogen} = \frac{\text{Titre Value} \times 0.1 \text{ MHCL} \times 0.014 \times 100 \times V_1 V_2}{\text{Weight of Sample}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Where V_1 = Volume of Digest (50ml) and,

V_2 = Volume of Digest Used (5ml)

$\% \text{ Crude Protein} = \% \text{ Nitrogen} \times 6.25$

3.5.2 Determination of crude fibre

The sample (1 gramme) was weighed into the flask (W_1) and boiled with 1.25% H_2SO_4 (150ml) for 30mins. The mixture was filtered through a poplin cloth and rinsed with distilled water; the residue was then scrapped back into the flask and boiled with 150ml of 1.25% NaOH for 30mins. The residue was collected again and rinsed with distilled water, 10% HCL and lastly with Ethanol. The residue was later scrapped into crucible. Oven dried, cooled in the desiccators, weighed (W_2) and ashed in the muffled, then reweighed (W_3).

$$\% \text{ Crude fibre} = \frac{W_t \text{ after oven drying } (W_2) - W_t \text{ after removal from furnace } (W_3)}{W_t \text{ of sample } (W_1)} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

3.5.3 Determination of Ether extract

Filter paper was weighed (W_1) and 0.5g each of the oven dried diet sample was place into the weighed filter paper and weighed again (W_2). The filter paper with the content was neatly folded, tied using thread and arranged in the thimble. Round bottom flask (500ml capacity) was filled with n-hexane up to $\frac{3}{4}$ of the flask. The extractor was fitted with the reflux condenser and heated to allow the solvent boil gently siphon several times within 8hrs. Samples were then removed dried in the oven for one hour at $105^{\circ}C$ cooled in the desiccators and weighed (W_3)

$$\% \text{ Ether Extract (Fat)} = \frac{\text{Loss in weight of the sample } (W_2 - W_3)}{\text{Weight of dried sample } (W_2 - W_1)} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

3.5.4 Determination of ash

Dry and clean crucibles were weighed (W_1) and their respective weight recorded, 1g of the sample were added and weighed again (W_2). The crucibles and content were placed into the muffle furnace at $550^{\circ}C$ until a light grey colour of ash was obtained. The crucibles were removed and allowed to cool in the desiccators and weighed (W_3).

$$\% \text{ Ash} = \frac{\text{Weight of Ash } (W_2 - W_3)}{\text{Weight of Sample } (W_2 - W_1)} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

3.5.5 Determination of Nitrogen free extract

This refers to the soluble carbohydrate in the samples and it is determined by difference.

$$\% \text{ NFE} = 100 - (\% \text{ Ash} + \% \text{ Crude Fibre} + \% \text{ Crude Protein} + \% \text{ Fat}).$$

3.5.6 Determination of Organic matter (OM)

The addition of all soluble nutrients in the diet and it was being calculated as:

$$\text{OM } (\%) = \% \text{ Crude fibre} + \% \text{ Crude protein} + \% \text{ Ether extract}$$

3.5.7 Energy determination

The gross energy was determined against thermo-chemical-grade benzoic acid using combustion calorimeter (model: 2k combustion calorimeter). Each was analysed thrice. The gross energy was determined by the methods of Ekanayake *et al* (1999) as follows

$$\text{G.E. (KJ/100gDM)} = \% \text{ CP} \times 16.7 + \% \text{ lipids} \times 37.7 + \% \text{ CHO} \times 16.7$$

CHO = Carbohydrate; G.E. = Gross Energy

3.5.8 Fibre Fractions Determination

- **Neutral detergent fibre determination (NDF)**

Dry and clean crucibles (W_1) were weighed and 1g of the samples were added into a crucible and weighed (W_2), and 100ml of NDF solution with 0.5g of Sodium sulphite were added. Heated for 60 minutes to boil, then after filtered and washed 3 times with boiling water, then twice with acetone. Dried for 8 hours at 105°C and weighed (W_3). Ash in a muffle furnace at 550°C for 2 hours and allowed to cool in a desiccator and weighed again (W_4).

$$\% \text{ NDF} = \frac{\text{Weight of crucible} + \text{weight of residue} - \text{weight of crucible}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

- **Acid detergent fibre determination (ADF)**

Dry and clean crucibles (W_1) were weighed and 1g of the samples were added into a crucible and weighed (W_2), and 100ml of ADF solution with 0.5g of Sodium sulphite were added. Heated for 60 minutes to boil, then after filtered and washed 3 times with boiling water, then twice with acetone. Dried for 8 hours at 105°C and weighed (W_3). Ash in a muffle furnace at 550°C for 2 hours and allowed to cool in a desiccator and weighed again (W_4).

$$\% \text{ ADF} = \frac{\text{Weight of crucible} + \text{weight of residue} - \text{weight of crucible}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

- **Acid detergent lignin determination (ADL)**

ADL was prepared, crucible was placed in the glass tray, one end of the tray was 2cm higher, so acid will drain away from the crucibles, covered the content of the crucible with H_2SO_4 and stirred. The acid was filtered off after 3 hours and the content was washed with hot water until it is freed from acid. Crucible was dried overnight at 100°C and weighed. Ash in a muffle furnace at 500°C to 550°C for 3 hours and then cooled in a desiccator and was weighed

$$\% \text{ ADL} = \frac{\text{Weight of crucible} + \text{weight of residue} - \text{weight of crucible}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

$$\% \text{ Hemicellulose} = \% \text{ NDF} - \% \text{ ADF}$$

$$\% \text{ Cellulose} = \% \text{ ADF} - \% \text{ ADL}$$

3.6 Data analysis

Data obtained were subjected to One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25 and where significant differences exist, Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) of the same package will be used to compare the means.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 RESULTS

4.1 Chemical Composition of Experimental Diets and Concentrate Fed to WAD Goats

The chemical composition of the experimental diets and concentrate fed to WAD goats is presented in Table 4.1. The dry matter ranged from 88.03% (A) to 90.75% (B). The ether extract content of the diet ranged from 3.57% (A) to 7.78% (B). The crude fibre ranged from 9.78% to 25.76%. The highest value was observed in E (9.78%) while the least value was observed in A (25.76%). The crude protein content ranged from 9.49% to 25.86%, the highest value was observed in E while the least value was observed in diet A. The value of acid detergent fibre (ADF) ranged from 26.98% – 38.00%, the highest value was observed in A while the least was observed in E. The nitrogen free extract recorded ranged from 41.05% (B) to 55.29% (D). The acid detergent lignin (ADL) value ranged between 21.93% (T₅) to 28.78% (A). The neutral detergent fibre (NDF) gotten was between 30.57% - 75.52%, the highest value was observed in Diet A while the least recorded was gotten in E. Hemicellulose value ranged from 3.57% (C) to 37.52% (A). The cellulose ranged from 5.05% (E) to 11.30% (Conc.). The organic matter recorded ranged between 73.18% (B) while the least was 81.45% (A). The gross energy content of the diet ranged from 13.23% (Conc.) to 18.38% (D) therefore, the highest value of gross energy was observed in D while the least value was observed in A. The ash content ranged from 6.42% (A) to 17.50% (B).

Table 4.1: Chemical Composition of Experimental Diets Fed to WAD Goats

Parameters (%)	A	B	C	D	E	Conc.
Dry matter	88.03	90.75	89.68	89.14	89.18	88.99
Crude protein	9.49	12.97	16.44	16.55	25.86	12.38
Crude fiber	25.76	20.63	18.08	15.09	9.78	9.91
Ether extract	3.57	7.78	3.85	5.50	6.50	5.53
Ash	6.42	17.5	9.67	7.57	10.33	8.47
Carbohydrate	42.79	31.87	41.64	44.43	36.71	52.70
Organic Matter	81.61	73.25	80.01	81.57	74.83	80.52
Nitrogen free extract	54.76	41.12	51.96	55.29	47.53	63.71
Neutral detergent fiber	75.52	48.32	37.93	35.84	30.57	57.00
Acid detergent fiber	38.00	35.18	34.36	32.04	26.98	30.35
Acid detergent lignin	28.78	25.09	25.16	23.67	21.93	19.05
Hemicellulose	37.52	13.14	3.57	3.80	3.59	26.65
Cellulose	9.22	10.09	9.20	8.37	5.05	11.30
Gross Energy (KJ/100gDM)	14.86	15.00	15.32	15.93	18.38	13.23

abc = means within the same row with different superscripts are significantly ($P < 0.05$) different.

Conc= Concentrate, A=100% *Panicum maximum* (P100M0), B=75% *Panicum maximum* + 25% *Morus alba* (P75M25), C=50% *Panicum maximum* + 50% *Morus alba* (P50M50), D=25% *Panicum maximum* + 75% *Morus alba* (P25M75), E=100% *Morus alba* (P0M100)

4.2 Feed Intake (g/day) of gravid WAD goats fed experimental diets

Table 4.2 presents the feed intake indices of WAD goats fed experimental diets containing *Panicum maximum* and *Morus alba*. Results showed that the treatment had significant ($P < 0.05$) effects on forage intake, total feed intake and total dry matter intake in early pregnancy while concentrate intake and total dry matter intake were significantly ($P < 0.05$) affected by the treatment in mid pregnancy. However, only total dry matter intake was influenced ($P = 0.03$) by treatment effect in late pregnancy. Furthermore, goats placed on C had the highest feed intake compared to all other treatments in early pregnancy. In mid pregnancy, WAD goats placed on T₃ also recorded the highest FOI (617.80g), TFI (912.72g) and TDMI (488.69g) while the highest CONI (297.59g) was observed in WAD goats fed A. Also, C recorded the highest TFI (1049.17g) and TDMI (539.63g) while the highest FOI (755.67g) and CONI (298.19g) were observed in WAD goats fed D and A respectively.

Table 4.2: Feed Intake (g/day) of gravid WAD goats fed experimental diets

Parameters		A	B	C	D	E	P-value
Early	FOI	352.06 ± 1.08 ^d	363.03 ± 2.89 ^{bc}	373.44 ± 2.65 ^a	370.31 ± 2.57 ^{ab}	360.41 ± 3.94 ^{cd}	0.00
	CONI	244.07 ± 2.00 ^a	241.16 ± 2.39 ^{ab}	247.08 ± 0.49 ^a	232.01 ± 6.73 ^b	238.18 ± 1.87 ^{ab}	0.08
	TFI	596.13 ± 0.99 ^b	604.19 ± 3.53 ^b	620.52 ± 2.86 ^a	602.31 ± 7.29 ^b	598.59 ± 5.38 ^b	0.03
	TDMI	338.45 ± 1.42 ^b	331.98 ± 2.22 ^{bc}	356.63 ± 1.20 ^a	324.96 ± 6.08 ^c	342.57 ± 2.83 ^b	0.00
Mid	FOI	604.81 ± 2.00 ^a	603.84 ± 4.24 ^a	617.80 ± 2.44 ^a	609.99 ± 3.93 ^a	599.80 ± 12.83 ^b	0.39
	CONI	297.59 ± 0.10	295.36 ± 1.47	294.92 ± 1.28	294.62 ± 1.27	289.74 ± 2.31	0.04
	TFI	902.40 ± 1.93 ^{ab}	899.20 ± 5.50 ^{ab}	912.72 ± 3.54 ^a	904.61 ± 5.19 ^{ab}	889.54 ± 10.57 ^b	0.18
	TDMI	473.12 ± 0.62 ^b	458.06 ± 2.55 ^c	488.69 ± 1.93 ^a	457.38 ± 2.38 ^c	475.21 ± 2.66 ^b	0.00
Late	FOI	714.74 ± 13.94	728.26 ± 14.37	752.38 ± 13.85	755.67 ± 4.83	738.83 ± 24.40	0.37
	CONI	298.19 ± 1.29	293.99 ± 5.21	296.78 ± 2.24	289.94 ± 9.58	290.24 ± 5.07	0.76
	TFI	1012.93 ± 15.21	1022.25 ± 19.50	1049.17 ± 13.35	1045.60 ± 7.85	1029.06 ± 28.99	0.61
	TDMI	511.51 ± 5.93 ^{ab}	497.07 ± 9.23 ^b	539.63 ± 4.86 ^a	499.83 ± 7.74 ^b	526.03 ± 13.01 ^{ab}	0.03

abc = means within the same row with different superscripts are significantly (P<0.05) different.

A = *Panicum maximum* (100%); B = *Panicum maximum* (75%), *Morus alba* (25%); C = *Panicum maximum* (50%), *Morus alba* (50%); D = *Panicum maximum* (25%), *Morus alba* (75%); E = *Morus alba* (100%); CONI = Concentrate intake; FOI = Forage Intake; TFI = Total Feed Intake; TDMI = Total Dry Matter Intake.

4.3 Nutrient Intake of gravid WAD goats fed experimental diets

The nutrient intake of gravid WAD does fed with the experimental diets were shown in Table 4.14. All parameters observed were significantly influenced ($P > 0.05$) by treatment with the exception of the organic matter intake. The dry matter intake of does fed diet D (25% *Panicum maximum*+ 75% *Morus alba* (P25M75)) was the least (427.18g/day), while the highest intake of 461.46g/day was observed for goats fed diet C (50% *Panicum maximum*+ 50% *Morus alba* (P50M50)). The crude protein intake of the does was significantly ($P > 0.05$) different among the treatments and the observed value ranged from 87.49 g/day to 180.14 g/day, the least value was recorded for does fed diet A (100% *Panicum maximum* (P100M0)), while the goats fed diet E (100% *Morus alba* (P0M100)), had the highest value. The crude fibre intake value observed in goats fed diet E was the least (82.38g/day) while goats fed diet A had the highest value (171.18 g/day). The crude fibre intake decreased with increased inclusion of *morus alba* in the diets. The ether extract intake values observed ranged between 35.37 g/day and 51.87 g/day, diet A had the least value and diet E had the highest value. The value of ash intake observed in goats fed diet A (59.45g/day) was the least while goats fed diet B (75% *Panicum maximum*+ 25% *Morus alba* (P75M25)) had the highest value (122.27 g/day). The recorded values of nitrogen free extract ranged between 408.52g/day and 493.13g/day, it was least in goats fed diet B while goats fed diet D had the highest. The OM intake value ranged from 636.50/day in goats fed diet B (75% *Panicum maximum*+ 25% *Morus alba* (P75M25)) to 690.87g/day in goats fed diet D. The CHO intake of goats fed diet B was the least (325.82 g/day) while goats fed diet D was the highest (400.36g/day). The observed values of gross energy ranged from 119.77(KJ/100gDM) to 140.12(KJ/100gDM), the goats fed diet E had the highest value while the goats fed diet A had the least value. The NDF intake value ranged from 185.01g/day in goats fed diet E to 580.05g/day in goats fed diet A. The ADF intake of goats

fed diet E was the least (235.47g/day) while goats fed diet A was the highest (296.54 g/day). The ADL intake ranged from 176.08 g/day in goats fed diet E to 213.57g/day in goats fed diet A. Goats fed diet A had the highest hemicellulose intake (283.51g/day) and least in goats fed diet E (92.97g/day). Cellulose intake was least in goats fed diet E and highest in goats fed diet C, the cellulose intake was within the range of 59.39 g/day in goats fed diet E to 88.25 g/day in goats fed diet B.

Table 4.3: Nutrient Intake (g/day) of gravid WAD goats fed experimental diets

Parameters	A	B	C	D	E	P-Value
Dry matter	440.80 ± 2.53 ^{bc}	428.83 ± 4.41 ^c	461.46 ± 2.31 ^a	427.18 ± 5.39 ^c	447.74 ± 6.15 ^{ab}	0.00
Crude protein	87.49 ± 0.58 ^d	107.51 ± 1.21 ^c	130.11 ± 1.00 ^b	129.41 ± 0.85 ^b	180.14 ± 3.68 ^a	0.00
Crude Fibre	171.18 ± 1.36 ^a	143.93 ± 1.70 ^b	132.73 ± 1.10 ^c	114.24 ± 0.70 ^d	82.38 ± 1.46 ^e	0.00
Ether Extract	35.35 ± 0.23 ^e	59.24 ± 0.68 ^a	37.82 ± 0.24 ^d	46.86 ± 0.36 ^a	51.87 ± 0.96 ^b	0.00
Ash	59.45 ± 0.39 ^d	122.27 ± 1.44 ^a	79.85 ± 0.59 ^b	66.83 ± 0.55 ^c	81.57 ± 1.52 ^b	0.00
Nitrogen free extract	483.22 ± 3.28 ^a	408.52 ± 4.43 ^c	479.92 ± 3.18 ^a	493.13 ± 4.09 ^a	442.75 ± 7.31 ^b	0.00
Carbohydrate	385.75 ± 2.59 ^b	325.82 ± 3.51 ^d	389.20 ± 2.55 ^b	400.36 ± 3.37 ^a	351.48 ± 5.69 ^c	0.00
Organic matter	679.78 ± 4.76	636.50 ± 7.11	689.86 ± 4.88	690.87 ± 5.28	643.12 ± 11.23	0.00
Gross Energy	119.77 ± 0.85 ^d	121.32 ± 1.38 ^{cd}	125.98 ± 0.93 ^{bc}	128.13 ± 0.89 ^b	140.12 ± 2.67 ^a	0.00
Neutral detergent fiber	580.05 ± 4.24 ^a	185.01 ± 1.70 ^e	379.66 ± 2.33 ^b	362.37 ± 3.55 ^c	328.44 ± 4.92 ^d	0.00

Acid detergent fiber	296.54 ± 2.15 ^a	282.67 ± 3.22 ^b	284.44 ± 2.09 ^b	267.89 ± 2.00 ^c	235.47 ± 4.07 ^d	0.00
Acid detergent lignin	213.57 ± 1.59 ^a	194.41 ± 2.23 ^{bc}	199.41 ± 1.53 ^b	188.74 ± 1.29 ^c	176.08 ± 3.23 ^d	0.00
Hemicellulose	283.51 ± 2.09 ^a	147.95 ± 1.57 ^b	95.22 ± 0.31 ^c	94.48 ± 1.58 ^c	92.97 ± 0.91 ^c	0.00
Cellulose	82.96 ± 0.56 ^b	88.25 ± 0.98 ^a	85.03 ± 0.56 ^b	79.15 ± 0.71 ^c	59.39 ± 0.84 ^d	0.00

a, b, c, means within the same row with different superscripts are not significantly ($P < 0.05$) different.

A=100% *Panicum maximum* (P100M0), B= 75% *Panicum maximum* + 25% *Morus alba* (P75M25), C= 50% *Panicum maximum*+ 50% *Morus alba* (P50M50), D= 25% *Panicum maximum* + 75% *Morus alba* (P25M75), E= 100% *Morus alba* (P0M100)

4.4 Growth Performance of gravid WAD goats fed experimental diets

The performance characteristics of gravid WAD does fed the experimental diets were shown in Table 4.15. There were no significant ($P>0.05$) differences in the performance characteristics of the goats fed the experimental diets except for the dry matter intake. The initial weight of the goats ranged from 10.80kg to 13.67kg, the goats fed diet C had the least value of initial weight while the highest value was recorded for goats fed diet A. The observed final weight of the does fed the experimental diets ranged from 19.03kg (does fed diet A) to 21.80kg (goats fed diet E). The weight gain ranged from 5.37kg to 8.67kg, the goats fed diet A had the least value while the highest weight gain was observed in diet C. The daily weight gain of the goats fed diet A was the least (37.27g/day) while goats fed diet C was the highest (60.19g/day). The observed values of feed to gain ratio ranged from 14.38g/day to 27.58g/day, the goats fed diet C had the least while the goats fed diet A had the highest.

Table 4.4: Performance characteristics of gravid WAD goats fed experimental diets

PARAMETERS	A	B	C	D	E	P-value
Final Weight(Kg)	19.03 ± 0.26	19.67 ± 2.40	19.47 ± 1.79	18.93 ± 2.24	21.80 ± 0.64	0.76
Initial Weight(Kg)	13.67 ± 2.14	12.13 ± 1.35	10.80 ± 1.31	11.20 ± 1.74	13.20 ± 1.33	0.68
Weight gain(kg)	5.37 ± 1.92	7.53 ± 2.63	8.67 ± 0.48	7.73 ± 0.53	8.60 ± 1.25	0.61
Weight gain(g/day)	37.27 ± 13.31	52.32 ± 18.24	60.19 ± 3.34	53.70 ± 3.70	59.72 ± 8.67	0.61
Grass intake(g/day)	556.87 ± 4.94	564.77 ± 7.09	580.95 ± 6.11	578.43 ± 1.96	566.11 ± 13.66	0.23
Conc intake(g/day)	279.83 ± 1.02	276.70 ± 2.39	279.49 ± 0.93	272.03 ± 5.88	272.60 ± 1.98	0.28
Totalfeedintake(g/day)	836.69 ± 5.84	841.48 ± 9.47	860.44 ± 6.10	850.47 ± 6.54	838.71 ± 14.91	0.39
Drymatterintake(g/day)	440.80 ± 2.53 ^{bc}	428.83 ± 4.42 ^c	461.46 ± 2.31 ^a	427.18 ± 5.39 ^c	447.74 ± 6.15 ^{ab}	0.00

Feed gain ratio	27.58 ±	20.33 ±	14.38 ±	15.97 ±	14.66 ±	0.26
	7.18	6.47	0.72	1.01	2.12	

a, b, c, means within the same row with different superscripts are not significantly ($P < 0.05$) different.

A=100% *Panicum maximum* (P100M0), B= 75% *Panicum maximum* + 25% *Morus alba* (P75M25), C= 50% *Panicum maximum*+ 50% *Morus alba* (P50M50), D= 25% *Panicum maximum* + 75% *Morus alba* (P25M75), E= 100% *Morus alba* (P0M100)

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 DISCUSSION

5.1 Chemical Composition of Experimental Diets and Concentrate Fed to WAD Goats

The crude protein (CP) of the diet was sufficient to support the growth and production of WAD goats. The recorded crude protein content in the diets was above the critical 8% crude protein required by ruminants for optimum microbial activities in the rumen (Asaolu *et al.*, 2012). This implies that the diets were adequate to meet the protein requirement for ruminant thereby ensuring effective rumen function (Ibhaze *et al.*, 2016). However, the crude protein reported was lower than the value (25.08% CP) reported by Aye and Adegun (2010). It was observed that the protein contribution of *Morus alba* improved the protein quality of the diets. Hence *Morus alba* could be an alternative source of feed ingredients. Furthermore, the fibre contents may fill up the available space in the rumen coupled with slow rate of degradation in the rumen. The gradual reduction in the ether extract of the diets was adequate to enable the animals to carry out their metabolic activities. The fibre fraction contents of the diets suggested that the diets could be adequate to meet the fibre requirements of the animals for proper rumen function (Ibhaze *et al.*, 2016).

5.2 Feed Intake Indices of gravid WAD goats fed experimental diets

There were significant differences in TDMI among the treatment groups ($P < 0.001$). The effects of using multipurpose trees as supplement to basal grass diets on growth and survival rates of WAD sheep and goats have been reported (Mengistu, 2019). The high daily dry matter intake observed here is in agreement with the report of Osakwe and Udeogu (2007). A very important consideration in the utilization of nutrients by animals may be the synchronization of nutrients especially protein and energy. This had earlier been observed by Okah *et al.* (2012). The differences in the nature of browse plants and conditions of the experiment could be responsible for this. This finding was in line with Okoruwa *et al.* (2018) who asserted that there are better efficient utilization of feed and production outcomes of some browse and forage mixtures than in solely browse or forage.

David (2014) reported that energy requirement is affected by stage of production. The decrease in TDMI among goats at later stage of pregnancy is consistent with earlier reports (Ogunwole, 2004 and Ibhaze, 2015). This decrease could be as a result of high levels of oestrogen in the blood that may alter metabolism and hence reduce energy requirements (Forbes, 1995; Ibhaze, 2015), reduction in abdominal cavity as well as the space available for expansion of the rumen during feeding as the foetus increases in size (McDonald *et al.*, 1995; Ibhaze, 2015).

5.3 Nutrient Intake Indices of gravid WAD goats fed experimental diets

The total dry matter intake (TDMI), total organic matter intake (TOMI), total crude fibre intake (TCFI) and total nitrogen free extract (TNFE) intake were better ($P < 0.05$) in group fed with *Morus alba* and *Panicum maximum*. The DM intake obtained in this study is higher than that reported by Aderinola *et al.* (2018) who fed cassava peel and poultry manure to WAD goats. David *et al.* (2020) opined that intake is influenced by the rate, extent of ruminal digestion, the rate of passage and microbial digestion of treated cell wall. However, the result obtained in this study is in agreement with the report of Fadiyimu *et al.* (2016) who used *Moringa oleifera*, *Gliricidia sepium* and cassava foliage to feed West African Dwarf (WAD) goats. According to Grandl *et al.* (2016), variations in feed and nutrient intake can be attributed to differences in breed, body weight, types of diet and length of time spent on the diet. Tremblay and Bellisle (2015) also posited that feed intake is greatly influenced by the palatability of the feed and animals' level of productivity. Therefore, the value of nutrient intake recorded in this study could be attributed to palatability and acceptability of the diet to the goats. A very important consideration in the utilization of nutrients by animals may be the synchronization of nutrients especially protein and energy which had earlier been observed by Okah *et al.* (2012).

5.4 Growth Performance of gravid WAD goats fed experimental diets

The feed conversion ratio and weight gain of the goat were not influenced by the treatments. The higher weight gain obtained in the goat fed diet C (50% *Panicum maximum*+ 50% *Morus alba* (P50M50)) might be attributed to the palatability, high DMI and better digestibility of the diet as weight gain is dependent on these factors (McDonald *et al.*, 1995). Goats fed mulberry utilized their feed better compared to other goats. All the experimental animals had adequate total dry matter intake (DMI) which ranged from 427.18 to 467.46g/animal/day. These values were comparably higher to values ranging from 288.48 to 354.49 g/animal/day for WAD goats fed *M. oleifera*, *Gliricidia sepium* and *Leucaea leucocephala* dried leaves as supplements to cassava peels (Asaolu *et al*, 2012) and those fed mulberry and Elephant grass (Omotoso and Fajemisin, 2020). These values met the minimum daily DMI of 3% of body weight recommended for small ruminants (NRC, 1985).

CHAPTER SIX

6.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

6.1 Conclusion

From this study it can be concluded that *Panicum maximum* and *Morus alba* can trigger the expression of some certain protein when fed to West African Dwarf goats, which its influence can be seen on the nutrient intake and feed intake. Gravid Goats fed with *Morus alba* utilized the diet better. Therefore, it could enhance goat production. The inclusion of *Morus alba* does not have any adverse effect on the health of the animals.

6.2 Recommendations

From the study, I would recommend that;

- i. *Morus alba* can be incorporated with *P. maximum* with inclusion level of up to 100% in ruminant livestock feed, it is a good source of dietary protein when non-conventional feedstuffs is to be used in place of the conventional feed stuffs.
- ii. Farmers should be sensitized about the potentials of *Morus alba* and *Panicum maximum* combination in ruminant feeding for better performance of WAD goats.
- iii. Ruminant farmers should be encouraged to cultivate *Morus alba* to ensure its all year round availability.

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